

Gender Differences in the Health Status of Elderly People

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ABSTRACT: Even though there are particularities within every age group which can be applied to the entire population, the seniors constitute the population's most heterogeneous segment and their functioning differs more from one person to another in comparison with the case of other age groups, due to the different aging rhythm, genetic heritage, psycho-spiritual profile, life experience, familial and socio-cultural context that the person lives in, and the events experienced in one's life.¹ The existing studies point out that there is a great variability and individuality in what concerns the experiencing of the aging process and, implicitly, regarding the experiencing of the various needs and their satisfaction. Therefore, this paper attempts to focus on the elderly and explore the health care status based on gender.

KEY WORDS: community development, old age, family, community, social assistance, religion, society.

One of the agents that have a major contribution in determining the difference in experiencing the aging process is represented by the gender. The gender seems to have a significant effect on the third age people's life, experiences and satisfactions. It is safe to say that, generally, the third age-class is a different kind of experience for women and men.²

Nowadays, the aging of the population and the gender are prominent aspects of the international forums and important areas of the social demographical preoccupations. McMullin stated that there is “a remarkable absence of theoretical preoccupations concerning the relation between gender and aging.” (McMullin 1995) The interest for the gender often focuses on the elder people’s economical and social vulnerability. Many of these researches have focused on studying women (Gibson 1996). It is generally considered that women are more vulnerable in comparison to men (Afzal 1996; HelpAge International 2000; Metha 1997).³

Friedman and his collaborators (Friedman 2003) have identified in the specialty literature two hypotheses concerning the existence of a greater vulnerability of the third age women:

- *the perspective over the life course, highlighting the gender differences in early and late life periods* (Hatch 2000) This hypothesis affirms that the relative disadvantage of older women relates especially to the differences regarding the economical and nursing role that they have had over their entire life and the rewards they received for having accomplished them (Hoyman, 1999). Explaining the gender differences by reporting to the disadvantages of the previous status constitutes as well a limit of this approach. The advantages offered by the previous status are being ignored.
- *the double juggling hypothesis* In this perspective, the accent is *put* on the negative effects of occupying two stigmatizing status: being a woman and being an elderly one.⁴

Gender differences concerning the third age people’s mental state of health

The changes of mental health are the result of the effects induced by the age, having at their basis internal factors, such as heredity and hormonal changes, and external factors, such as retirement, the decrease of the biological potential, associated pathology, the

decrease of the number of family members and the death of some relatives or friends of close ages.

The specialty literature is dominated by the existence of three mental disorders at the third age people: depression, delirium and dementia. The evaluation of these disorders is performed through interviews, self description and description of the people within the elderly person's proximity, psycho-physiological methods and direct observations and evaluations of the performances.⁵

Gender differences concerning depression and depressive symptoms of old people

The depressive symptoms may occur as a response to the loss of a beloved person or of the feeling of control over his own life, as secondary effects of the existence of some chronic diseases or of the prescribed medication for other diseases and disorders. Schnittker (2005) outlined that those people who develop early chronic diseases and/or disabilities tend to experience even more depressive symptoms in comparison to those people who develop later chronic diseases and/or disabilities.⁶

Some of the studies on third age-class depression doubted the conviction that aging is related to high levels of depression (Charles, Reynolds & Gatz 2001).⁷ The epidemiological researches reveal that acute depression incidence is lower for the third age population in comparison to young adults. Even though there is a great variability in experiencing the depressive symptoms, variability that can be caused by the differences in gender and ethnicity too, in general, a decrease of depression once with the aging process is observed.

Some meta-analyses of the epidemiological studies concluded that the prevalence of slight or subclinical depression it is much more spread among the third age-class in comparison to major depression and the depression prevalence tends to decrease at advanced age.⁸ Ruegg and his collaborators concluded that the depressive symptoms of elderly people can often be obscured by somatic accuses and physical symptoms, which leads to them being overlooked, misdiagnosed and treated superficially. The depressive

symptoms are strongly related to a grown risk of functional disability, weak social support, an intensification of the use of care services and a negative state of well-being (Bruce et al.1994; Henderson et al. 1997; Pennix et al. 1998; Han 2002; cited. Katsumata, Arai, Ishida, Tomimori et al. 2005).⁹

Nguyen and Zonderman (2006) highlighted the fact that there is some degree of stability of the depressive symptoms in the case of people aged under 70. Even though the state of depression and the interpersonal issues remained stable, in the case of people aged over 70, there was an increase of somatic symptoms and a lack of well-being. No gender differences were noticed in the presented study.¹⁰

Silverstein and his collaborators (1999) stated that the depression prevalence is equal within both sexes and the depression's somatic subtype is more prevalent in the case of women. Some studies offered empirical support for Silverstein's hypotheses (Nolan & Wilson 1994, Kornstein et al. 2000, Frank et al. 1998; Young et al. 1990).

Generally, the studies revealed that the symptoms of major and atypical depression are more prevalent in women case in comparison to men (Weissman & Klerman 1977; Vasquez-Barquero et al. 1992; Dewey et al. 1993; Kessler & al. 1993; Weissman et al. 1993; Stechtman et al. 1997; Zunzngui et al. 1998; Prince et al. 1999; Zunzunegui, Minicuci, Blumstein, Noale et al. 2007.) The researchers brought up for discussion various biological and psychosocial reasons concerning the existing gender differences (Piccinelli & Wilkinson, 2000).¹¹

As for the elderly population, Forsell and his collaborators, analyzing the depressive symptoms distribution, ascertained that women manifested more depressive symptoms related to the disposition, while elderly men had more depressive symptoms related to the motivation.

Kockel and Heun (2002) examined the gender differences concerning the experiencing the depressive symptoms in the third age people case. The data obtained from the 236 elderly participants diagnosed with depression before the age of 50 and 357 participants from the general population revealed that women from the general population manifested more depressive symptoms as compared

to men, especially appetite and joyfulness disorders. The gender differences concerning the number of depressive symptoms from the general population were fully explained by the gender differences concerning the psycho-social variables, such as the familial status. As for the elderly people, there was no identification of gender differences concerning the number of depressive symptoms.

Women and men diagnosed with major depressive disorder presented a distinct profile of the depressive symptoms which could not be fully explained by psycho-social factors. The depressive elderly women manifested more appetite related disorders, while elderly depressive men reported they were more agitated. The explanations invoked by the study's authors for these results outline the possibility for women to present a different subtype of depression or to have differences of perception and expression of the depressive symptoms.¹²

Major depression at the third age-class appears under some partially different symptoms in the case of men and women. These results suggest that the gender differences concerning the experiencing of major depression symptoms at the elderly population reflect gender differences in the depressive symptoms perception and expression.

Preventing and reducing depressive symptoms have an important role in maintaining a high level of life quality for the elderly population. Identifying the depression's risk factors is useful both for planning some adequate prevention strategies and for improving the knowledge base concerning the treatment of depressive symptoms in the community that elderly people are part of. Among the risk factors significantly associated to the depressive symptoms at elderly people we can include the physical disability, the deficit of social support and isolation, the appearance of some life stressing events and the presence of chronic diseases (Beekman et al., 1995, Prince et al., 1997).¹³

Djernes (2006), while making a review of the relevant publications and of those from MEDLINE and Psychinfo data base, ascertained that the main predictors of the depressive disorders and of the depressive symptoms are: feminine gender, somatic diseases,

cognitive diseases, functional disease, the lack or loss of close social contacts and the historic of a depression.¹⁴

Katsumata and his collaborators (2005) examined the gender differences concerning the contribution of some risk factors to the depression's appearance at the third age population, using a sample of 665 elderly Japanese people. The evaluated risk factors were the demographic features, health status and disability, stress and the social networks. The depressive symptoms were evaluated using 30 items from the Geriatric Depression Scale (Brink et al. 1982; Yesavage et al. 1983; Niino et al. 1991). This study's results indicate the fact that the stress risk factor contributed the most to the explanation of the depressive symptoms variance at men and the health status and disability were the best in explaining the depressive symptoms variance at elderly women (see Appendix 2).¹⁵

Sicotte and his collaborators (2008) revealed that close social relationships are associated with a lower prevalence of depressive symptoms, independently of the stressors' presence. Those women who were or are married, live in extended families and develop close social relationships with relatives and children manifest a lower prevalence of depressive symptoms. Men manifested less depressive symptoms if they were married and didn't live alone.¹⁶

Special attention should also be given to the way in which elderly people's gender influences the management of depression. Some studies highlighted the fact that elderly women receive less medical intervention in the case of major disorders, as compared to men (Ethical and Legal Affairs Council, American Medical Association 1991, Ayanian & Epstein 1991; Ramani, Byrne-Logan, Freund, Ash, Yu & Moskowitz 2000; McMahon, Wolfe, Huang, Tedeschi, Manning & Edlund 1999).¹⁷

Frayne and his collaborators (2004) examined the way in which the gender of the elderly population influences the the management of depression performed by the doctors who are taking care of them. The results of the study they have made with the help of a *stratified random sample of 243* doctors revealed the fact that the patient's gender does not influence the recommendations for the management of depression made by the doctors both for the young elderly people (ages 67–79) and for the old elderly people (aged over 79).¹⁸

Gender differences in the anxiety of older people

Fuentes and Cox (2000) examined the gender differences regarding anxiety within a sample of 132 elderly participants, 39 women and 45 men. Women obtained a higher score on anxiety as a feature as compared to men (see Appendix 3). Using a sample of 636 elderly participants aged 56 to 103, Reybolds and his collaborators (2003) identified significant gender differences under the aspect of manifest, chronic anxiety.¹⁹

Gender differences in the older people's posttraumatic stress dynamic

Numerous epidemiological studies revealed that the posttraumatic stress (PTSD) tends to become more prevalent among women as compared to men (Breslau & Davis, 1992; Kessler, Sonnega, Bromet, Hughes & Nelson 1995). Other studies focused on identifying the causes that determine a different experiencing of this disorder by women and men. The incriminated causes were:

- women tend to experience more traumatic events
- women tend to experience different types of traumatic events (more severe or pathogen events, perhaps)

The studies that have been made starting from these hypotheses did not always provide empirical support for the existence of gender differences in experiencing posttraumatic stress.²⁰ On the contrary, other studies highlighted the fact that men tend to experience more traumatic events as compared to women.²¹ The gender studies' inconclusive results can be also attributed to some methodological problems, such as:

- the use of convenience samples
- the use of different assessment tools for posttraumatic stress (semi-structured interviews, questionnaires, for example)

Analyzing numerous articles that have been published over the course of 25 years, Tolin and Foa achieved an ample quantitative review of these, trying to provide some conclusive results concerning gender differences related to genus and posttraumatic stress disorder. The meta-analyses concerning the gender specific risk of experiencing potentially traumatic events and the posttraumatic stress disorder indicated that the women participants manifest a higher probability to match the DSM criteria for posttraumatic disorder as compared to male participants, even though the former experience less traumatic events. The two authors outlined that the gender explains just partially the differences between the two sexes in the risk for experiencing the traumatic events and the generated stress.²²

Gender differences in older people's alcohol consuming

The excessive alcohol consumption contributes to increasing the risk for the type II diabetes (Wannamethee, Shaper, Perry & Alberti 2002), coronary diseases, cardiac arrhythmias and the risk of other diseases' appearance, too (Bartholow, Sher & Krull 2003).

Schonfeld and Dupree (1994) evidenced that about 60 % of the USA's 35 millions elderly people consume alcohol at least occasionally. Numerous studies evidenced the apparition of abusive alcohol consumption in the late adult age-class. Most of the researchers estimate that 10 % of the elderly people have had episodes of abusive alcohol consumption (Mirand & Welte 1996; Hays, Greendale, Damesyn & Reuben 1999). The abusive alcohol consumption within the elderly population could be dangerous due to the physical changes that concern the way in which alcohol is distributed and processed. The risk of adverse interactions presented by the medication-alcohol interactions increases due to the increased number of medication that elderly people take. The alcohol could cause additional problems such as falls, accidents, too.²³

Wiscott, Kopera-Frye and Begovic (2002) evaluated the differences between alcohol consuming young-elderly people and old-elderly people. The results revealed that the old-elderly people are 15.7 times less predisposed to abusive alcohol consumption as

compared to the young-elderly people. Elderly women were 19.7 times less predisposed to abusive alcohol consumption, in general. Due to the differences concerning the composition of the body and metabolism of the alcohol, elderly women who abusively consume alcohol have an increased risk of confronting various negative aspects such as depression.²⁴

Gender differences in the third age people's suicide

The risk factors that contribute to the elderly people suicide include the aging process, male gender, physical diseases, social isolation (Parker, Cantrell & Demi 1997), widower status and psychiatric disorder (Barraclough 1971; Lindsay 1991; Cattell & Jolley 1995; Baldwin 1997; Harwood & Jacoby 2000; cited. Salib & Green 2003), substances abuse, especially alcohol (Bird & Hutchinson 2003). From these factors, the age and the gender are the most associated to suicide. Generally, men appeal more often to suicide compared to women and elderly people have an increased suicidal rate compared to younger people.²⁵

The studies confirmed gender differences concerning the suicidal behavior, elderly men having an increased suicidal rate compared to elderly women (Breed and Huffine 1972; Cattell 1988; Conwell et al. 1991; Cattell and Jolly 1995; Quan 1999; Harwood & Jacoby 2000). In male gender people's case, the suicidal risk increases especially after their wives or life partners' death. (Bock and Webber 1972; Cattell and Jolley 1995; Li 1995; Harwood and Jacob 2000), social isolation being a risk factor (Bock and Webber 1972). Conwell and Duberstein (2001) outlined that another elderly men group presenting an increased suicidal level is of the ones who don't have active contacts with the staff providing healthcare services.²⁶

Salib and Green (2003) came with a review that examines third age people's gender differences concerning specific social aspects of the suicidal act and contacting the care services before suicide. Data revealed that male gender people had less knowledge concerning psychiatric services and they reported less suicidal attempts compared to female gender people. There were no differences between men

and women on physical and psychiatric morbidity, the frequency of contacts with the generalist doctor, isolation and lonely living.

Parker, Cantrell and Demi (1997) examined the attitude of the elderly people towards suicide, being especially interested in gender and race differences concerning this subject. The participants manifested a moderate level of empathy for the suicidal behavior and a low level of agreement for the suicidal actions. There were no gender or race differences concerning the empathy for the suicide people or for the suicidal acts. There were no identifications of significant interaction effects between race and gender on attitudes about suicide.²⁷

Gender differences in taking decision related to health

The efficiency of deciding process declines once with the aging process. Usually, third age people don't try to find out too many information about decisional alternatives and tend to rely on what they already know. This domain performances become weaker and weaker, compared to the young people ones, in those situation when elderly people are requested to be creative or inventive in their decisions, in lesser known areas for them.²⁸ Due to some problems like the poor medical practice and the lack of emphasis the importance of the patient's autonomy, we are witnessing a dramatic change of how treatment decisions are taking place in current medical contexts (Pierce 1996). Currently, medical treatment is more patient-oriented and the patients are more involved in the selection of treatment, especially in areas where there are several treatment options such as breast or prostate cancer (Davison & Degner 1997).²⁹

Meyer, Talbot and Ranalli (2007) conducted two studies that examined if elderly people take faster decisions in comparison with young people about treatments for breast and prostate cancer. The results showed that the elderly take immediate decisions compared to young people. This research is important not only because it demonstrates the effects of age regardless of domain consistency, gender, ethnic group, education, but also because it investigates a model that tries to explain the effects of age on decision making. Data

indicate that when making decisions about medical treatments that they should follow, elderly people rely on their treatment knowledge, interest and involvement and cognitive resources. These reasons relate to different ways of processing information about treatment and preferences for immediate or delayed decisions. People who had a rich store of knowledge about immediate treatment have taken immediate decisions. Instead, people who possessed more cognitive resources and showed a greater interest in the types of treatment took late decisions. In the presented study no gender differences were found among elderly people in terms of speed of decisions about medical treatments they could opt for.³⁰

Gender differences in the medicines costs

The consequences of diseases of third age people are the emergence of additional medicines costs and longer or shorter hospitalization, food deprivation, reduced mobility and in more severe cases, even the loss of autonomy in some degree, problems exacerbated by the lack or reduction of medicines' accessibility and healthcare assistance. Money for medicines is a financial burden for the elderly people. Some researches have shown that women tend to spend much more money for medicines compared with men (Blustein 2000; Gibson & Foley 2000; Mojtabai & Olfson 2003). This can be explained by several factors, including the gender differences on use, receipts coverage and financial income.

Elderly women require more often receipts prescription (Mojtabai & Olfson 2003; Moon & Herd 2002; Poisal & Murray 2001). Many women do not have financial coverage for receipts, having a relatively low income (Sambamoorthi, Shea & Crystal 2003).

Gender differences in the informational functioning of the elderly people

In terms of speed and efficiency of information processing, they decrease with age and depend on the processing level and task's

particularities. The possible explanations for the decreasing speed of informational processing are represented by the fact that at every level of informational processing more information is lost compared to young people's situation.³¹

Many researchers have shown that this cognitive decline is not uniform, since the changing patterns present a great intra- and inter-variability.³²

Gender differences in the attentive functioning

The attentive deficit and the mental slowing have a major role in the age related decline of several cognitive abilities (Albert 1988; Craick & Byrd 1982) and they have been associated with Alzheimer's dementia, even in its average forms (Nestor, Parasuraman, Haxby & Grady 1991). Studies in this area highlighted a decrease in efficiency of voluntary attention, but not for the involuntary one, too.³³

In the third age-class, a decline of attention's focusing capacity is observed (Filley & Cullum 1994).

Although some studies have found that normal aging does not cause changes in attention, Mazaus and his collaborators (1995) found out that third age people showed reduced attentive skills and a lower speed of execution once with aging. Female gender and low education level were related with a weaker functioning of the attentive processes and operating performance.³⁴

Gender differences in the loneliness and isolation of elderly people

The third age period is often seen as a time of loneliness.³⁵ The loneliness was defined as the subjective complaint against the interpersonal relations that occurred from changing the current social relationship or from changing needs and desires for relationships (Peplau & Perlman 1982). The loneliness occurs when relationships do not satisfy social needs, when they fail to fulfill personal desires or when social rewards lower.³⁶

The researches have shown that loneliness is more frequent as people get closer and closer to the moment of death (Penninx et al. 1997).³⁷ The loneliness is closely linked with isolation, low education level, low income, death of somebody significant and unemployment (Fischer & Philips 1982), celibacy (Weiss 1975, 1976). The personality's variables associated with loneliness include: low self-esteem, shyness, feelings of alienation, locus of external control and the conviction that the world is not a rightful place (Jones, Freeman & Goswick, 1981), inhibited sociability (Horowitz & French 1979), boredom, anxiety and unhappiness (Perlman, Gerson & Spinner 1978), suicide (Jacob 1971; Wenz 1977), physical illness (Lynch 1976), depression (Bragg 1979; Schultz & Moore 1984), low assuming of the social risk and low motivation affiliation (Russel, Peplau & Cutrona 1980; Schultz & Moore 1984) and self-criticism (Loucks 1980). The studies concerning the interpersonal dimensions of loneliness indicated that single people evaluated themselves and evaluated the others negatively and expect others to negatively evaluate them, too (Jones et al. 1981). Alone people tend to evaluate themselves as having a high self-awareness, as being unfriendly, unaccepted by the others and unattractive for the opposite sex (Jones et al. 1981), they make internal negative attributions, particularly in interpersonal situations (Anderson 1983; Anderson, Horowitz & French 1983).³⁸

Wenger and Burholt (2004) found that isolation and loneliness are associated with a poor physical health, depressions and diseases that are devastating for the elderly people (Rokach, Matalon, Rokach & Safarov 2007). In general, the loneliness is related to isolation, negative disposition, inadequate assignments and deficient social skills. However, these relationships are moderated by age and gender (Schmitt & Kurdek 1985). The elderly people often face a variety of eating disorders (Roy, 1986), friends or life partner's death, (Rabasca, 1999) and various degrees of social isolation (Delisle 1988). These circumstances, these life events affect the way elderly people live their life, they evaluate and confront the demands of life.³⁹

Rokach, Matalon, Rokach and Safarova (2007) conducted a research that explored the qualitative aspects of loneliness of the third age people. The data were obtained from 89 men and 239

women, participants from both categories having the age between 61 and 94 years. The five qualitative aspects of the evaluated loneliness in this study were: emotional distress, inadequacy and social alienation, growth and breakthrough, social isolation and self-alienation. The results confirmed the hypothesis that elderly women live the loneliness differently than men. The female people' scores were significantly higher in the scale of growth and breakthrough. This indicates that women are more likely to perceive the positive aspects of loneliness. For the other aspects of loneliness no gender differences have been identified. The comparisons performed in order to determine whether marital status affects living the loneliness, indicated that married elderly men obtained lower scores on interpersonal isolation scale compared with unmarried elderly men.⁴⁰

Schmitt and Kurdek (1985) examined the age and gender differences in terms of personality correlated with loneliness in different social relationships: familial, friendship, romantic/sexual, and in larger groups. Compared with young women, the third age people showed a higher level of satisfaction for their relationships with family members and those belonging to the larger groups they are part of. Instead, the elderly people said they were less satisfied with their relations of friendship.⁴¹

NOTES

¹ Maria E. Sorescu, *Third age people social assistance*. Craiova: Craiova's University Publishing House, 2005.

² A. Rokach & F. Neto, (2005). "Age, culture and the antecedents of loneliness," *Social Behavior and Personality* 33/5 (2005): 477-494.

³ J. Friedman, J. Knodel, B. T. Cuong, & T. S. Anh, "Gender dimensions of support for elderly in Vietnam," *Research on Aging* 25 (2003): 587-629.

⁴ N. L. Chappell, "Health and helping networks among the elderly. Gender differences," *Journal of Aging and Health* 1 (1989): 102-120.

⁵ A. Muntean, *The Psychology of human development*, Iași: Polirom Publishing House, 2006.

⁶ J. Schnittker, "Chronic illness and depressive symptoms in late life," *Social Science & Medicine* 60 (2005): 13-23.

⁷ S. T. Charles, C. A. Reynolds, & M. Gatz, "Age-related differences and change in positive and negative affect over 23 years," *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 80 (2001): 136–151.

⁸ H. T. Nguyen, A. B. Zonderman, "Relationship between age and aspects of depression: Consistency and reliability across two longitudinal studies," *Psychology and Aging* 21.1 (2006): 119–126.

⁹ K. Katsumata, A. Arai, M. Tomimori, K. Denda, H. Tamashiro, "Gender differences in the contribution of risk factors to depressive symptoms among the elderly people dwelling in a community, Japan," *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry* 20 (2005): 1084–1089.

¹⁰ H. T. Nguyen, A. B. Zonderman, "Relationship between age and aspects of depression: Consistency and reliability across two longitudinal studies," *Psychology and Aging* 21.1 (2006): 119–126.

¹¹ M. Kockler, R. Heun, "Gender differences of depressive symptoms in depressed and non-depressed elderly people," *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry* 17 (2002): 65–72.

¹² M. Kockler, R. Heun, "Gender differences of depressive symptoms in depressed and non-depressed elderly people," *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry* 17 (2002): 65–72.

¹³ K. Katsumata, A. Arai, M. Tomimori, K. Denda, H. Tamashiro, "Gender differences in the contribution of risk factors to depressive symptoms among the elderly people dwelling in a community, Japan," *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, 20 (2005): 1084–1089.

¹⁴ J. K. Djernes, "Prevalence and predictors of depression in populations of elderly: a review," *Acta Psychiatr. Scand.* 113 (2006): 372–387.

¹⁵ K. Katsumata, A. Arai, M. Tomimori, K. Denda, H. Tamashiro, "Gender differences in the contribution of risk factors to depressive symptoms among the elderly people dwelling in a community, Japan," *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, 20 (2005): 1084–1089.

¹⁶ M. Sicotte, B. E. Alvarado, E.-M. León, M.-V. Zunzunegui, "Social networks and depressive symptoms among elderly women and men in Havana, Cuba," *Aging & Mental Health*, 12.2 (2008): 193–201.

¹⁷ S. M. Frayne, K. M. Skinner, H. Lin, A. S. Ash, K. M. Freund, "Effects of patient gender on late-life depression management," *Journal of Womens's Health*, 13.8 (2004): 919–925.

¹⁸ *Idem*, 62.

¹⁹ P.A. Lowe, C. R. Reynolds, "Do relationships exist between age, gender, and education and self-reports of anxiety among older adults?" *Individual Differences Research* 3.4 (2005): 239–259.

²⁰ R. M. Giaconia, H. Z. Reinherz, A. B. Silverman, B. Pakiz, A. K. Frost, E. Cohen, "Traumas and posttraumatic stress disorder in a community population of older adolescents," *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry* 34 (1995): 1369–1380.

- ²¹ N. Breslau, R. C. Kessler, H. D. Chilcoat, L. R. Schultz, G. C. Davis, P. Andreski, "Trauma and posttraumatic stress disorder in the community: The 1996 Detroit Area Survey of Trauma," *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 55 (1998): 626–632.
- ²² D. F. Tolin, E. B. Foa, "Sex differences in trauma and posttraumatic stress disorder: A quantitative review of 25 years of research," *Psychological Trauma, Theory, Research, Practice, and Policy* (2008): 37–85.
- ²³ L. Schonfeld, L. W. Dupree, "Alcohol abuse among older adults," *Reviews in Clinical Gerontology* (1994): 217–225.
- ²⁴ R. Wiscott, K. Kopera-Frye, A. Begovic, "Binge drinking in later life: Comparing young-old and old-old social drinkers," *Psychology of Addictive Behaviors* 16.3 (2002): 252–255.
- ²⁵ C. Pritchard, L. Hansen, "Comparison of suicide in people aged 65–74 and 75+ by gender in England and Wales and the major Western countries 1979–1999," *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry* 20 (2005): 17–25.
- ²⁶ E. Salib, L. Green, "Gender in elderly suicide: analysis of coroners inquests of 200 cases of elderly suicide in Cheshire 1989–2001," *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry* 18 (2003): 1082–1087.
- ²⁷ L. D. Parker, C. Cantrell, A. S. Demi, "Older adults' attitudes toward suicide: Are there race and gender differences?" *Death Studies* 21 (1997): 289–298.
- ²⁸ A. Muntean, *Psychology of Human Development*, Iași: Polirom Publishing House, 2006.
- ²⁹ B. J. F. Meyer, A. P. Talbot, C. Ranalli, "Why older adults make more immediate treatment decisions about cancer than younger adults," *Psychology and Aging* 22.3 (2007): 505–524.
- ³⁰ B. J. F. Meyer, A. P. Talbot, C. Ranalli, "Why older adults make more immediate treatment decisions about cancer than younger adults," *Psychology and Aging* 22.3 (2007): 505–524.
- ³¹ A. Muntean, *Psychology of Human Development* (Iași: Polirom Publishing House, 2006), 425.
- ³² P. B. Baltes, "Theoretical propositions of life-span developmental psychology: On the dynamics between growth and decline," *Developmental Psychology* 23.5 (1987): 611–626.
- ³³ V. Bucur, A. Macivan, "Third age people problems," in G. Neamțu (ed.) *Social Assistance Treaty*, Iași: Polirom Publishing House, 2003.
- ³⁴ J. M. Mazaus, J. F. Dartigues, L. Letenneur, D. Darriet, L. Wiart, M. Gagnon, D. Commenges, F. Boller, (1995). "Visuo-spatial attention and psychomotor performance in elderly community residents: Effects of age, gender, and education," *Journal of Clinical and Experimental Neuropsychology* 17.1 (1995): 71–81.
- ³⁵ M. Jylha, "Old age and loneliness: Cross-sectional and longitudinal analyses in the Tampere longitudinal study on aging," *Canadian Journal on Aging* 23.2 (2004): 157–168.
- ³⁶ A. Rokach, F. Neto, "Age, culture, and the antecedents of loneliness," *Social Behavior and Personality* 33.5 (2005): 477–494.

³⁷ A. Rokach, R. Matalon, B. Rokach, A. Safarov, "The effects of gender and marital status on loneliness of the aged," *Social Behavior and Personality* 35.2 (2007): 243–254.

³⁸ A. Rokach, F. Neto, "Age, culture, and the antecedents of loneliness," *Social Behavior and Personality* 33.5 (2005): 477–494.

³⁹ *Idem*, 105.

⁴⁰ A. Rokach, R. Matalon, B. Rokach, A. Safarov, "The effects of gender and marital status on loneliness of the aged," *Social Behavior and Personality*, 35.2 (2007): 243–254.

⁴¹ J. P. Schmitt, L. A. Kurdek, "Age and gender differences in and personality correlates of loneliness in different relationships," *Journal of Personality Assessment* 49.5 (1985): 487–496.